

HOSILANI GEOMETRIK MASALALARNI YECHISHDA TADBIQI

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litseyi matematika fani o'qituvchilari

Annotatsiya: Hosila mavzusi o'rta maktab va akademik litseylarda Algebra fanidan o'tiladi. Lekin geometriya fanida gapirilmaydi. Hozirgi kunda matematikadan milliy sertifikat, hamda attestatsiya savollarida geometriya fanidan qo'yilgan savollarni yechish masalasi hosila mavzusida borib taqaladi. Shu maqsadda ushbu maqolada geometriyadan masalalar yechishda hosilani tadbqiqiga doir masalalar yechib ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Hosila, grafik, masala, yechim, eng katta, hajim.

Hosilani hayotda tadbqiqi juda ko'p uchraydi. Geometrik jismlarni o'lchamlarini yasamasdan oldin hosila yordamida aniqlanadi. Shuning uchun geometriya fanidan masalalarni yechishda hosiladan foydalanamiz.

Masala-1. Tomonlari 21 va 16 ga teng bo'lgan to'g'ri to'rtburchak shaklidagi tunkaning to'rtta uchidan tomoni h ga teng bo'lgan kvadrat qirqib olindi quti shakliga keltirildi. Qutining hajmi eng katta bo'ladigan h ni toping.

Berilgan:

$$BC=16$$

$$AK=KM=h$$

$$KN=16-2h$$

$$FF_1=16-2h$$

$$h=?$$

Yechish: Shakil to'g'ri burchakli parallelepiped shakliga keladi eng katta hajimga ega bo'lish uchun quyidagi formulani olamiz:

$$V(h)=(21-2h)(16-2h)h$$

bu ifodani soddalashtirsak

$$V(h)=336h-74h^2+4h^3$$

ko'rinishga keladi. Ifodadan hosila olamiz va $V'(h)=0$ tenglamani yechamiz.

$$V'(h)=336-148h+12h^2$$

$$12h^2-148h+336=0 |:4$$

$$3h^2-74h+84=0$$

bundan $h_1=3$ va $h_2=9\frac{1}{3}$ yechimlar chiqadi.

Masala shartiga ko'ra $h=3$ bo'lganda eng katta hajimga ega bo'ladi.

Masala-2. Radiusi R ga teng bo'lgan yarim aylanaga $CDEF$ to'g'ri to'rtburchak ichki chizilgan S_{CDEF} ning eng katta qiymatini toping.

Berilgan:

R

$S_{CDEF} \max - ?$

Yechish: $EF=b$, $OF=\frac{a}{2}$ $\triangle OFE$ dan $R^2=b^2+\frac{a^2}{4} \Leftrightarrow 4R^2=4b^2+a^2$ tenglikdan $a=2\sqrt{R^2-b^2}$

$$S=ab=2b\sqrt{R^2-b^2}=2\sqrt{b^2R^2-b^4}$$

$S(b)=2\sqrt{b^2R^2-b^4}$ ifodadan hosila olamiz.

$$S'(b)=\frac{2bR^2-4b^3}{\sqrt{b^2R^2-b^4}}$$

$S'(b)=0$ deb yechamiz $2bR^2-4b^3=0$ va $\sqrt{b^2R^2-b^4} \neq 0$ tenglikdan $b=\frac{R}{\sqrt{2}}$

$$a=2\sqrt{R^2-\frac{R^2}{2}}=\sqrt{2}R$$

$$S_{CDEF}=\sqrt{2}R \cdot \frac{R}{\sqrt{2}}=R^2$$

Javob: R^2

Masala-3. Radiusi $6\sqrt{2}$ ga teng bo'lgan sharga ichki chizilgan eng katta hajmli konus asosining radiusini toping.

Berilgan:

$$AO=6\sqrt{2}$$

$$AD=R-?$$

Yechish: ΔAOD dan $AO^2 = AD^2 + OD^2$

$$(6\sqrt{2})^2 = R^2 + (H - 6\sqrt{2})^2$$

$$72 = R^2 + H^2 - 12\sqrt{2}H + 72$$

$$12\sqrt{2}H - H^2 = R^2$$

$$V_k = \frac{1}{3}\pi R^2 H = \frac{1}{3}\pi(12\sqrt{2}H - H^2)H = 4\sqrt{2}\pi H^2 - \frac{1}{3}\pi H^3$$

$$V_k = 4\sqrt{2}\pi H^2 - \frac{1}{3}\pi H^3 \text{ ifodadan hosila olamiz.}$$

$$V'(H) = 8\sqrt{2}\pi H - \pi H^2 = \pi H(8\sqrt{2} - H)$$

$$V'(H) = 0 \text{ dan } \pi H \neq 0 \text{ va } H = 8\sqrt{2}$$

$$R^2 = 12\sqrt{2} \cdot 8\sqrt{2} - 128 = 12 \cdot 16 - 128 = 64$$

$$R^2 = 64 \Leftrightarrow R = 8$$

Javob:8.

Masala-4. Sharga eng katta hajmli silindr ichki chizilgan R– shar radiusi, r– silindr asosi radiusi.

a)

$\frac{r}{R}$ nisbatni toping.

b)

Shar hajmining silindr hajmiga nisbatini

toping.

Berilgan:

$AO = R$ – shar radiusi

$AE = r$ – silindr asosi radiusi.

$$OE = \frac{H}{2}$$

$$\frac{r}{R} \text{ --?}, \frac{V_{sh}}{V_{sil}} \text{ --?}$$

Yechish:

$$\text{dan } R^2 = r^2 + \frac{H^2}{4} \Leftrightarrow 4R^2 = 4r^2 + H^2 \Leftrightarrow 4R^2 - H^2 = 4r^2$$

$$r^2 = R^2 - \frac{1}{4}H^2 \quad (1)$$

$$V_{sil} = \pi r^2 H = \pi \left(R^2 - \frac{1}{4}H^2 \right) H = \pi R^2 H - \frac{\pi H^3}{4}$$

ΔAEO

$$V_{\text{sil}} = \pi R^2 H - \frac{\pi H^3}{4} \text{ ifodadan hosila olamiz}$$

$$V'_{\text{sil}}(H) = \left(\pi R^2 H - \frac{\pi H^3}{4} \right)' = \pi R^2 - \frac{3\pi}{4} H^2$$

$$V'_{\text{sil}}(H) = 0 \text{ tenglikdan } \pi R^2 - \frac{3\pi}{4} H^2 = 0 \Leftrightarrow H = \frac{2R}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (2)$$

(2) ifodani (1) ifodaga qo'yamiz

$$r^2 = R^2 - \frac{R^2}{3} = \frac{2R^2}{3} \Leftrightarrow r = \frac{\sqrt{2}R}{\sqrt{3}} = \frac{\sqrt{6}R}{3}$$

$$a) \frac{r}{R} = \frac{\sqrt{6}R}{3} : R = \frac{\sqrt{6}}{3}$$

$$b) V_{\text{sh}} = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 \quad V_{\text{sil}} = \pi r^2 H = \frac{4\sqrt{3}\pi R^3}{9}$$

$$\frac{V_{\text{sh}}}{V_{\text{sil}}} = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 : \frac{4\sqrt{3}\pi R^3}{9} = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 \cdot \frac{9}{4\sqrt{3}\pi R^3} = \frac{3}{\sqrt{3}} = \sqrt{3}$$

Javob: a) $\frac{\sqrt{6}}{3}$ b) $\sqrt{3}$

Masala-5. Apofemasi $3\sqrt{3}$ ga teng bo'lgan muntazam to'rtburchakli piramida hajmining eng katta qiymatini toping.

Berilgan:

SABCD – muntazam piramida

$$SE = 3\sqrt{3}$$

$V_{\text{max}} = ?$

$$\text{Yechish: } \Delta SEO \text{ dan } SE^2 = SO^2 + OE^2 \Leftrightarrow (3\sqrt{3})^2 = H^2 + \frac{a^2}{4}$$

$$108 = 4H^2 + a^2 \Leftrightarrow a^2 = 108 - 4H^2$$

$$V_p(H) = \frac{1}{3} a^2 H = \frac{1}{3} (108 - 4H^2) H = 36H - \frac{4}{3} H^3$$

$$V_p(H) = 36H - \frac{4}{3} H^3 \text{ ifodadan hosila olamiz.}$$

$$V'_p(H) = 36 - 4H^2 \text{ tenglikdan } 36 - 4H^2 = 0 \text{ tenglamadan } H^2 = 9 \Leftrightarrow H = 3$$

$$a^2 = 108 - 36 = 72$$

$$V_p = \frac{1}{3} a^2 H = \frac{1}{3} \cdot 72 \cdot 3 = 72$$

Javob: $V_{\text{max}} = 72$

Xulosa: Geometriya fani o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodni kamol toptirishda o'quv fani sifatida keng imkoniyatlarga ega. U o'quvchi tafakkurini rivojlantirib, ularni aqlini peshlaydi, uni tartibga soladi, o'quvchilarga maqsadga yo'naltirilganlik, mantiqiy fikirlash topqirlik

xislatlarini shakillantirib boradi. Shunday ekan masalalar matematika mutaxassisligida ta'lim olayotgan talabalar va o'quvchilarning hosila yordamida geometrik masalalarni yechishda qo'yiladigan talablarni oson o'rganishga yordam beradi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. I.Isroilov, Z.Pashayev "Geometriya" Toshkent-2010.
2. Sh.Jumayev, B.Ro'ziyev va boshqalar "Geometriya" Toshkent-2024.
3. 2025-yil BMBA savollar to'plami.